

Path2Integrity questionnaire for students with an academic degree and researchers (graduates)

Instructions

During this evaluation, we kindly ask you to respond to the following case scenarios about research practices. Each case scenario starts with a short description followed by 4 steps which build on one another. Only one option can be chosen for each question.

First decide which action is in line with good research practices and then use the slider to indicate how confident you feel about your answer.

Please choose a reason for your answer by choosing the option that best suits your opinion and then use the slider to indicate how confident you feel about your answer.

Please note that you cannot return to a previous page of the survey! But you may always skip a question, stop the survey, or withdraw from it completely.

For her first research project at the university, Olivia wants to ensure that she knows how exactly research should be done and what considerations she has to take into account. To follow good research practices Olivia ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- reviews what she has been taught in high-school.
- just starts and learns by doing it.
- looks for examples in the press.
- looks at the university's guidelines for good research practices.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Olivia's decision complies with good research practices because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- it ensures reliable research results.
- everyone does it like this.
- research must not be restricted by rules.
- it saves valuable resources.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Salim has conducted interviews for his research project on misconduct at the university. He found that at least some of his colleagues had used questionable research practices. When he presents the first results at an internal colloquium, a discussion is sparked on how to proceed with this knowledge. To follow good research practices, Salim ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- should listen to all points of view and then decide according to his own convictions.
- should stop the discussion.
- should not have presented the results at all.
- should listen to all points of view, weigh them up, and decide on the basis of the best arguments.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Salim's action is in line with good research practices because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- this decision allows him to justify his analysis step by step.
- this decision ensures equal treatment in research.
- it will enhance his reputation to do so.
- there are no relevant binding codes and regulations that say otherwise.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

David wants to conduct a research project but realises that there are many different methods mentioned in the literature. To ensure good research practices, David should ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- use the method that seems most appropriate for his research.
- use the method with which he is most familiar.
- use the method that is most commonly used.
- use the most prestigious method.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

David's decision is in line with good research practices because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- the majority does so and David must follow.
- it ensures responsible conduct of research.
- it is the duty of David to do so.
- since there are no binding regulations, he can do so.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Ahmed has observed his fellow researcher Susie falsifying data in a research project. Ahmed wants to follow good research practices and informs the ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- ombudsperson / research integrity officer.
- police.
- ethics committee.
- public relations department.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Ahmed's decision is in line with good research practices because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- it ensures equal treatment of all misconduct cases.
- it complies with codes and regulations in research.
- it is Ahmed's duty.
- it protects the reputation of Ahmed's organisation.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Ivana is invited to be a member of the research integrity committee. She is asked to participate in hearings on a new misconduct case. To act in accordance with good research practices, Ivana accepts the invitation because...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- she has experience in committee activities.
- she is impartial.
- she often does voluntary work.
- she knows the case well.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Ivana's decision is in line with good research practices because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- it helps ensure the reliability of research results.
- it will decrease the damage to the university from having a case of misconduct.
- this decision ensures equal treatment of research.
- it will enhance her reputation to do so.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Bill, who is from a Greek university, is collaborating with Lorenzo, the research project leader, who is from a university in Finland. Their institutions follow different codes of conduct. To follow good research practices, they ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- both use the code of their own institution.
- have to use the code applicable to the project leader.
- have to use an international code of conduct.
- agree on a code that applies for both of them.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Their decision is in line with good research practices, because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- this ensures collaborative work in research.
- as the majority does so, they have to follow this practice.
- this decision ensures equal treatment in research.
- the legal framework does not allow them to act in any other way.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Sven wants to write a paper for a journal regarding his research project. For this he is going to paraphrase from other texts. To follow good research practices, Sven refers to the original source ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- with a reference at the end of the paraphrased section.
- by enclosing the section in quotation marks.
- by using quotation marks and a reference at the end of the quote.
- only with a reference in the bibliography at the end of the paper.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Sven's decision is in line with good research practices, because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- as the majority does so, Sven also has to follow this practice.
- this ensures recognition of the source and the original author.
- this decision ensures equal treatment in research.
- there are no relevant binding codes and regulations.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Gabriela is writing a paper about her research project for a journal. For this, she wants to use the description of the content that she has written for a previous paper. To follow good research practices, Gabriela ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- must rewrite the part from the earlier paper.
- can reuse her own work without citing herself.
- has to ask the journal editor for permission to quote it.
- should quote the part from the earlier paper or cite herself.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Gabriela's decision is in line with good research practices because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- it ensures the appropriate presentation of the source and the original author.
- the majority observes this practice and Gabriela also has to follow it.
- it is Gabriela's duty to do so.
- since there are no binding regulations, she can do as she wishes.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Clarke has recently become the mentor of William, who is very insecure. To follow good mentoring practices, Clarke should ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- always be honest with William, even if it means questioning his results.
- not let William do anything alone.
- leave William on his own.
- determine that William must attend a class for self-confidence.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Clarke's decision is in line with good research practices because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- the legal framework for mentoring requires it.
- since Clarke is the expert it is his duty to do so.
- because that's his role as a superior.
- it helps establishing high quality research results.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Elena conducts interviews with teachers from a local school. She remembers that Professor Aya said something about the storage of data. To ensure that she works according to good research practices, Elena has to store ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- all data necessary for traceability.
- as much data as possible.
- only personal data.
- all data relevant for publication.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Elena's decision is in line with good research practices because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- due to the complexity and variety of research, it must be done this way.
- it is the duty of Elena to follow this process.
- the legal framework governing universities requires it.
- it ensures reliable research results.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

In his research project, Ali has collected a large amount of research data that he would like to make available open access in accordance with the FAIR principles. To follow good research practices Ali ensures that his data ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- are described with rich metadata to be machine-readable.
- are stored on FAIR foundation servers.
- can be found in every database possible.
- do not contain any information about sexual orientation.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident

Ali's decision is in line with good research practices because ...

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- it ensures the equal treatment of all research data.
- it is the duty of Ali to follow this process.
- the legal framework governing universities requires it.
- it ensures reliable research results.

How confident are you about your answer?

Please enter a value between 1 and 100, where 1 stands for very unsure and 100 for very confident.

- |very unsure|very confident